

RESULTATS ACCIONS DE SENSIBILITZACIÓ

RESULTS OF THE BEACH CLEAN UPS

Dates i lloc

Dates and place

Dates

16 d'abril
26 d'abril
21 de maig
27 de maig
18 de juny

Participació

Turnout

En total van participar **153** persones

In total, 153 people were involved

Quants residus hem obtingut?

How much residues were collected?

En total es van recollir més de **40 Kg** de residus

In total, more than 40 Kg of waste were collected

Quins residus hem obtingut?

Which residues were collected?

Quins residus peculiars hem obtingut?

Which unusual residues were collected?

Xeringues

Needles

Peces Lego

Lego pieces

Mapa

Map

Globus

Balloon

Coixí

Pillow

RESULTATS ACCIONS DE SENSIBILITZACIÓ

RESULTS OF THE BEACH CLEAN UPS

Dates i lloc

Dates and place

Dates

16 d'abril (snorkel i submarinisme)
21 de maig (snorkel)
18 de juny (snorkel)

Participació

Turnout

En total van participar **30** persones

In total, 30 people were involved

Quants residus hem obtingut?

How much residues were collected?

Quins residus hem obtingut?

Which residues were collected?

Quins residus peculiars hem obtingut?

Which unusual residues were collected?

Mòbil
Phone

Globus
Balloon

Piles
Batteries

Fregall
Scrubber